

IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF PERSONNEL TRAINING IN THE FIELD OF FOOD PRODUCTION

Shahlokhon Karimovna Gafurova

Teacher of Bukhara State University, Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11445432>

Abstract. *In recent years, the category of quality in education is becoming more and more economic, as the image of higher education is formed as an industry that provides relevant services in the modern market, has its own consumer, and produces a certain product. In order to maintain the competitiveness of the products produced in the food sector, the educational institution must maintain its quality at the required level. It should be noted that the problem of the quality of education is undoubtedly an important part of the national education policy, so each higher education institution should have its own quality model in relation to the general problem of managing the quality of education.*

Keywords: *quality management, competency, labor market, ISO standards, Total quality management, TQM principles.*

The ongoing globalization of the world economy has led to the creation of internationally integrated economic systems and the development of information, communication and green technologies. These profound changes in the economy have also affected the education system: traditional methods of education and knowledge assessment have changed, new specialties and training areas are being formed, mobility of students and teachers is increasing, the difference between leading universities with high human resources, research resources, modern laboratory facilities, information and communication technologies and other universities that do not meet the current level of knowledge is growing. The employability of students who have received higher education depends on the professional knowledge, skills and competencies they have acquired, which meet the requirements of the labor market. Therefore, the task of higher education institutions is to constantly improve educational programs based on the study of demand for higher education services and the needs of employers, to integrate internships and on-the-job training into educational programs, to develop partnerships with industry.

Quality assurance is the most important function of modern higher education. It is necessary to establish quality management systems of higher education institutions based on the new version of the international standard ISO 9001:2015, based on the process approach, PDCA cycle and risk-based thinking. To ensure the quality and integrity of education, faculty should have the opportunity for research and knowledge acquisition from various sources. Greater flexibility in the organization of research systems is needed so that science and interdisciplinarity can better serve the needs of all sectors of society.

The evolving labor and science market requires regular revision of competences and maintaining the consistency of learning outcomes and their assessment, while paying attention to supra-disciplinary competences that enable graduates to successfully enter the profession.

In the formation of competences, it is necessary to choose forms of training and assessment criteria in which students better achieve the required competence, and feedback from students is of great help.

In the above classification, general competences are divided into three groups: instrumental, interpersonal and systemic.

Instrumental competences include competences that serve as a tool for wider use of professional and specialized competences for greater manifestation:

- cognitive abilities to understand ideas and theory;
- methodological abilities to organize working conditions and make decisions;
- technological abilities in the use of technical devices, information management and computer skills;
- linguistic abilities in the field of communication in the native language and knowledge of a foreign language.

Interpersonal competences include competences that determine the abilities to: express ideas and critically evaluate actions; function in a social environment;

- interacting with other individuals and working in a team.

Instrumental and interpersonal competences serve as a basis for acquiring systemic competences. Systemic competencies define the ability to: be receptive to knowledge and understanding; make combinations from the whole to the individual and see the interrelationships of the parts; and be able to plan changes to improve the systems in question.

Depending on the context, some competencies can be universal and can be used to describe both general and professionally specialized competencies. For example, knowledge and understanding of English serve as instrumental skills and at the same time as professional competencies for students specializing in this field.

The proposed generic competencies are not equally important for different education profiles. Some may be necessary and relevant for all types of higher education, such as the ability to analyze and synthesize, while others have a private, specific application. In one educational program the key competence is teamwork, in another the emphasis is on independent work and decision-making.

The main potential that ensures the innovative development of Uzbekistan's economy is embodied in higher education institutions, and its level is directly determined by the quality of higher education. Therefore, one of the important goals of reforms in the education system of Uzbekistan is aimed at improving quality. The quality of higher education as a priority is reflected in the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. According to this document, the government sets for the higher education system the task of "training highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking, independent decision-making personnel based on international standards, creating the necessary conditions for them to demonstrate their intellectual abilities and develop as morally mature individuals." So, it can be noted that the concept of "education" has the meaning of developing and forming a person, that is, it is aimed at meeting the social, cultural, economic and other needs of the person, society and the state as a whole. From this point of view, in the approach that reveals the content of the quality of modern education, the main criterion is the level of satisfaction of the needs of the individual and society, and its conformity with the needs of the individual and society. This approach is based on defining the quality of education in terms of its ability to meet the needs of consumers and recipients of educational services. On the other hand, the issue of personnel training based on "international standards" is raised. Therefore, the educational quality management system should be built taking into account the requirements of international standards (ISO 9001:2000) and the principles of total quality management (Total Quality Management) at the institutional level.

The reason we come to this conclusion is that from the point of view of the task set by the government, the concept of TQM and the concept of ISO do not exclude each other, but complement each other. In this case, if the ISO standards are intended to regulate the relationship between the producer and the consumer, the concept of TQM is intended to solve the internal problems of university. ISO standards answer questions about what to do to ensure quality, and TQM principles - how to do it.

Without dwelling on the history of the formation of ISO standards in detail, we can say that today about 25 standards have been developed in the ISO 9000, 10000 series, which contain standards and requirements that must be satisfied by activities in the field of quality management.

Based on the analysis of TQM practices and the 2000 standards of the ISO 9000 series, we have summarized eight quality management principles underlying the standards and related to the TQM concept.

Principle 1. A consumer-oriented organization. The prosperity of any organization or enterprise depends on the volume of sales of their products or services, which in turn depends on the compliance of these products (services) with the needs and requirements of consumers. All employees of the organization must know and understand the needs and expectations of consumers.

Principle 2. The role of leadership. Above all, senior managers must demonstrate their commitment to quality by their personal example.

Principle 3. Recruiting employees. People form the most important and valuable part of the organization, so the best use of people's capabilities can bring maximum benefit to the organization.

Principle 4. Approach as a process. It primarily refers to an algorithmic approach to the design of a quality management system as a set of interrelated processes.

Principle 5. Systematic approach to management. This is closely related to the previous principle and the view of the quality management system as a set of interrelated processes. A systematic approach also includes continuous improvement of the system through measurement and evaluation.

Principle 6. Continuous improvement. Continuous or constant improvement is one of the goals of the enterprise. The principle of continuous improvement requires knowledge and application of relevant methods and approaches such as the Deming cycle, Pareto analysis, control charts, etc.

Principle 7. A fact-based decision-making method. This principle is an alternative to the way decisions are made in practice, often based on intuition, feeling, past experience, assumptions, etc. Decisions are effective if they are based on data and information analysis.

Principle 8. Mutually beneficial relations with partners. It is clear that there is an interdependence between the organization and its partners, and it is also clear that a mutually beneficial relationship offers the best opportunities for both parties.

The above-mentioned principles should be used when creating a quality management system within HEIs. But, as we mentioned earlier, the quality management (TQM) system based on ISO 9000, on the one hand, is universal and designed for use in different conditions. ISO requirements, on the other hand, are mainly for the production network, which focuses on the production of products and services that are different but have some common characteristics. The analysis of the educational process showed that it has many similarities with any production process, but there are also fundamental differences. Educational services provided by higher

education, that is, training of highly educated specialists in one or another field, have a special feature.

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